

Machine Learning in Agriculture

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Fig. 1 [12]

Abstract

If we as species are going to survive, farming is the humanity's very foundation we must adapt. Technology is changing the way we do farming, not with least powerful computers but computers powered with Machine Learning Algorithms. ML provides knowledge to farmers in the form of Crop Management, Soil health and Weather facts. This technology enhances crop production yields by a lot to guide farmers with decisions on when and where farming choices are made, including what to plant, how much water we have to use for irrigation and effective pest control. ML increases output not by just using resources well and cutting waste, it also helps in convenience for farming to last more so that we can find enough what we eat to feed millions in a healthy manner.

Introduction

In the last few years, the agricultural sector has, in fact, passed through a technological change characterized by increasing integration of machine learning and deep learning techniques. Such advanced technologies are contributing to the solution to critical challenges: from improving crop yield to plant disease detection and weed control. Especially with the rise in global population and the consequence of that on food production with the adversities of climate change, ML and deep learning find promising applications in agriculture for enhancing productivity by effectively optimizing resources.

Crop yield prediction is one of the critical applications of ML in agriculture and, therefore, assumes paramount importance as far as food security is concerned. These would, in turn, enable farmers to make informed decisions on strategies for planting and resource use that would enhance agricultural production. Among the researchers working on crop yield prediction using both ML and DL models, the best score was achieved by one using the Random Forest algorithm-98.96%. The same study also utilized CNNs, and these performed very impressively with a very minimal loss of 0.00060, which showcases a very high degree of precision in yield forecasting (Predicting_Agriculture...). These results will mean a lot to regions where agricultural productivity is bonded to climatic variability and other unpredictable factors.

Fig.2 [13]

Besides yield prediction, ML and DL technologies have been applied for enhancing crop quality and weed control, other complementary areas of interest in the process of value maximization of agricultural products. The very same deep learning models, like YOLOv3 and CNN, hold immense potential for identification of weed and diseases with high accuracy. These models can analyze a huge amount of data that may come from drones and sensors,

detect, and classify various plant diseases and weeds in real time. This way, interventions would be more focused, reducing the use of excess pesticides and minimizing the ecological footprint of farming. For example, CNN-based models were successfully applied to precision weed control, allowing differential application of herbicides with potential great reduction in the environmental impact of agriculture (Revolutionizing_Agricul...).

Fig. 3 [14]

A thorough review of ML uses in agriculture in the last two decades gives the same picture—a rise in the role of those technologies in this sector. It highlights how ML has been applied in disease detection and yield prediction, livestock management, soil, and water resource management amongst others. Machine Learning algorithms in this area include Support Vector Machines, Artificial Neural Networks, and K-Nearest Neighbors, each used in different agricultural domains of interest and at the same time improving productivity along with efficiency. Besides this promising outcome, several challenges remain to be overcome. Where used training datasets are of poor quality, agricultural data are sparse, noisy, or imbalanced.

Computational cost: The training of complex deep learning models, such as CNNs and LSTMs, is extremely costly. Such models require a lot of computational resources in terms of powerful hardware and large datasets to be able to perform with high accuracy. Given the resource-constrained environment in small-scale farms, access to these might be limited, hence not being able to apply them widely. While DL models, such as CNNs, perform very well on image-based data sets by recognizing patterns, when applied in complex or noisy environments, for example, in real-world agricultural settings, their performance may degrade.

Despite these challenges, the integration of ML and DL in agriculture has enormous potential. The idea is of a future wherein these evolving technologies have come to integrate completely into agriculture, monitoring crops, predicting yields, and managing resources with very little human intervention. This not only increases farmers' productivity but also enables the making of agriculture more sustainable with minimal wastage and maximum utilization of resources. With more and more real-time data from IoT devices, satellite imagery, among others, the predictive powers of ML models are bound to improve in the future, hence enabling forecasting and timely interventions in better ways in crop management.

Literature Review

From the above, it is clear how machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) integration is changing the face of agriculture: it is equipping farmers with cutting-edge information to predict yields for crops, detect diseases in plants, weed management, and quality improvement.

- I. **Random Forest:** Random Forest is a very robust and accurate algorithm of ML that is highly preferred for agricultural predictions. Application of Random Forest has been shown to result in 98.96% accuracy in crop yield prediction in the paper titled Predicting Agriculture Yields Based on Machine Learning Using Regression and Deep Learning. Therefore, this makes it one of the most effective methods for crop yield prediction. This algorithm aggregates the results of multiple decision trees and avoids overfitting simultaneously and improves the performance of the model on noisy data sets.
- II. **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs):** CNNs are a type of deep learning models that have been identified to be particularly effective for image-based data useful for agricultural applications like detection of diseases and weed control. In the same study, CNNs was integrated into Random Forest to demonstrate excellent performance by holding a very low minimum loss value of 0.00060, thereby suitability for crop yield prediction. CNNs have also been applied to real-time plant disease detection and weed management through processing drone and sensor images. For instance, in Revolutionizing Agriculture: Machine and Deep Learning Solutions for Enhanced Crop Quality and Weed Control, CNN-based models have been used in that precise herbicide application is realized with a minimal environmental footprint.

- III. **YOLOv3:** Another deep learning algorithm that is applied in agriculture is the YOLOv3, You Only Look Once, in object detection tasks. Real-time detection is actually a specialty of YOLOv3, and agricultural environments require fast decision-making processes. This includes, for example, the applications that use the algorithm in targeting. This can be shown through the example of reducing broad-spectrum pesticides.
- IV. **SVMs:** SVM is an ML algorithm that has on several occasions been applied for the classification and regression tasks especially in agriculture. Some of the applications for SVM include disease detection and yield prediction among many. SVM offers the best hyperplane that can differentiate between different classes and, therefore this algorithm distinguishes itself especially when the data points cannot be separated using a linear separator. Review: Machine Learning in Precision Agriculture: A Survey on Trends, Applications, and Evaluations Over Two Decades, emphasized SVMs for applications in a variety of agricultural areas especially crop quality prediction and water management.
- V. **Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs):** ANNs are one of the basic building blocks used by most deep learning architectures. It is a simulation of the structure of human brains and helps one realize patterns in large datasets. ANNs have found applications in quite a few agricultural fields, for example, observing soil and crop yield prediction. In the Machine Learning in Precision Agriculture literature review, it was established that ANNs are highly flexible and thus are applicable in numerous applications including forecasting yield and disease detection. ANN models are, however, costly in terms of resources and consume volumes of data unless large computational capabilities are available to train them adequately.
- VI. **K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN):** KNN is a simple algorithm yet a valid technique that is mainly used for the classification of agriculture particularly new data points. It classifies new data according to the majority class that exists among their nearest neighbors within the training dataset. The algorithm has been applied in crop yield prediction as well as disease detection. For example, in Revolutionizing Agriculture, KNN was applied in classification of weeds and proved successful in differentiating the different forms of weeds.
- VII. **Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Networks:** LSTMs are a type of RNNs that learn long term dependencies in sequential data, thus it is best used for time series predictions such as crop yield forecast based on historical data. In the article Predicting Agriculture Yields, LSTMs were utilized to predict crop yields although they gave less competence performance compared to CNNs and RF because of the complexity of agricultural datasets.

LSTMs are useful where past contexts, for example, historical records on weather patterns, are significant to future events, like crop output.

- VIII. **Decision Tree:** Perhaps the most frequently applied algorithm in agriculture is called the Decision Tree, a name which refers to another popular supervised learning methodology, preferably used for classification and regression problems. It is one of the simplest algorithms and can be used to model very complex decision-making processes if there is data available. On agricultural farms, it is used to predict the yield of crops, including the input factors such as rainfall, temperature, and soil type. In one experiment, Decision Trees are used to predict the agricultural yield with the accuracy of 89.78% and thus prove their feasibility to be applied on multiple inputs and thereby produce credible predictions based upon past data.
- IX. **XGBoost Regression:** XGBoost Regression is also one of the most important machine learning algorithms widely applied in agriculture on regression tasks. As the task is the prediction of continuous values such as crop yield. XGBoost is a gradient boosting algorithm where the models are developed sequentially to correct the errors made by the preceding models. It has also been applied in agriculture to analyse big data concerning meteorological conditions, soil properties, and crop characteristics. For example, XGBoost has been used to predict crop yields with an accuracy of 86.46 percent. However, it performed its prediction just a little less effectively than other algorithms like Random Forest. It highly computationally efficient and hence suitable for big data analysis in precision agriculture.
- X. **LeNet:** One of the class models in deep learning is the LeNet; originally designed for digit recognition, later on, they were optimized and used in different projects related to agriculture. Examples include classification for plant diseases. LeNet has number of convolutional layers followed by fully connected layers of network; hence it can learn image data patterns. In agricultural, the use of LeNet has been in classifying plant diseases from the image processing of leaves that tends to discover the early signs of infections. A benchmark whose experiment on banana leaf classification used LeNet got accuracy ratings between 92% and 99% for the model, showing that the algorithm is capable of even the smallest visual recognition in datasets that come from agriculture.
- XI. **Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM):** Gradient Boosting Machines are other ensemble learning algorithms, like XGBoost, which can be applied in agriculture. GBM builds models successively by maximizing a loss function. The GBM algorithm has been used to model the non-linear relations of environmental variables to crop outputs. GBM cannot compete with XGBoost for the speed perspective but is very efficient when used for moderately sized

datasets in the specific task of yield prediction. It has proved strong predictor in yielding crop productivity and managing soil properties that make the useful tool in the decision-making process for resource allocation.

XII. Deep Belief Network (DBN): A deep belief network is a generative graphical model made up of multiple layers of hidden, stochastic units, which can learn to reconstruct its inputs. In agriculture, DBNs have been successfully applied to the prediction of crop productivity. This is one example where DBNs were used for forecasting the yields of five crop crops in the region of Karnataka, which include rice and ragi. The complex nature of agricultural datasets with interrelating factors was thus shown to be enabled by DBNs. DBNs provided for accurate predictions about yield productivity while considering many factors that range from climate conditions to soil quality.

Comparative Table

Paper Title	Author Year	Machine Learning Algorithm	Dataset	Result Accuracy	Advantages	Challenges	Remarks
Evaluation of Machine Learning Approaches for Precision Farming in Smart Agriculture System: A Comprehensive Review	Ghulam Mohyuddin, Muhammad Adnan Khan, Abdul Haseeb, Shahzadi Mahpara, Muhammad Waseem, And Ahmed Mohammed Saleh 2024	1. Deep Learning (DL) 2. K-means clustering 3. Various traditional data mining techniques combined with DL models	Various datasets for precision farming.	The study shows improved accuracy using Deep Learning (DL) combined with K-means features, achieving up to 92.89% accuracy	High accuracy with DL and K-means Integrates multiple techniques for robust solutions	Complex implementation Data quality dependency	This paper combines traditional data mining techniques with DL to enhance plant disease detection and classification.

Machine Learning and Deep Learning for Plant Disease Classification and Detection	Vasileios Balafas, Emmanouil Karantoumanis, Malamati Louta, And Nikolaos Ploskas 2023	DenseNet121 GoogLeNet AlexNet YOLOv5 Lightweight YOLOv5 with Ghostnet and BiFPN	PlantVillage and PlantDoc datasets.	High accuracy in real-time classification	High accuracy Applicable to various datasets and diseases	High computational demand Generalization issues	This paper provides a comprehensive evaluation of state-of-the-art classification and object detection algorithms, highlighting the trade-off between accuracy and training time.
Weed Density and Distribution Estimation for Precision Agriculture Using Semi-Supervised Learning	Shantam Shorewala, Armaan Ashfaque, R. Sidharth, And Ujjwal Verma 2021	Semi-supervised learning with classification model.	Mixed datasets depending on application	Focus on minimizing misclassification; specific values not detailed.	Reduces manual annotation effort. Effective for precise weed management.	High computational cost for processing large image datasets. Potential for misclassification in complex field conditions.	Effective for site-specific weed management, reduces manual annotation effort
Machine Learning in Precision Agriculture: A Survey on Trends, Applications and Evaluations Over Two Decades	Sarah Condran, Michael Bewong, Md Zahidul Islam, Lancelot Maphosa, Lihong Zheng 2022	Decision Trees, Random Forest, SVM, ANN, KNN	Surveys various datasets used in precision agriculture over the last two decades.	Discusses the accuracy of multiple ML models across different agricultural applications, noting improvements over time.	Addresses key data challenges like class imbalance and high dimensionality.	Inherent challenges with agricultural data, such as sparsity and noise, which complicate ML applications.	Provides a comprehensive overview of the evolution and impact of ML in agriculture, identifying trends and challenges.

<p>Revolutionizing Agriculture: Machine and Deep Learning Solutions for Enhanced Crop Quality and Weed Control</p>	<p>Syed Mujtaba Hassan Rizvi, Asma Naseer, Shafiq Ur Rehman, Sheeraz Akram, Volker Gruhn</p> <p>2023</p>	<p>SVM, CNN, YOLOv3 for object detection, KNN for weed classification</p>	<p>Various datasets focusing on crop quality and weed control, gathered from different agricultural studies.</p>	<p>High accuracy achieved with advanced ML techniques for both crop quality improvement and weed control.</p>	<p>Enhances crop quality and weed control through advanced ML techniques.</p>	<p>Requires high-quality, balanced datasets for optimal performance.</p>	<p>The paper highlights the effectiveness of ML in enhancing agricultural practices while maintaining environmental sustainability.</p>
<p>Predicting Agriculture Yields Based on Machine Learning Using Regression and Deep Learning</p>	<p>Priyanka Sharma, Pankaj Dadheech, Nagender Aneja, Sandhya Aneja</p> <p>2023</p>	<p>Random Forest, Decision Tree, XGBoost Regression, CNN, LSTM</p>	<p>Data from 1997 to 2020 on crops, meteorological conditions, and agricultural parameters from official Indian government websites.</p>	<p>Random Forest: 98.96% accuracy CNN: Minimum loss of 0.00060</p>	<p>High accuracy with Random Forest (98.96%) and minimal loss with CNN.</p>	<p>Data complexity due to the need for integrating multiple data sources.</p>	<p>The study shows that Random Forest and CNN are highly effective for predicting crop yields in India.</p>
<p>AgriFusion: An Architecture for IoT and Emerging Technologies Based on a Precision Agriculture Survey</p>	<p>Ritesh Kumar Singh, Rafael Berkvens, And Maarten Weyn</p> <p>2021</p>	<p>Supervised (Regression, Classification), Unsupervised (Clustering, PCA), Deep Learning (CNN)</p>	<p>The paper references several datasets used for crop yield, disease detection, and quality prediction like CropDeep.</p>	<p>High accuracy models like deep neural networks (DNN) showed improved results in predicting crop growth and yield.</p>	<p>Improved decision-making, better crop management through prediction models, real-time data analysis.</p>	<p>Challenges include data acquisition complexity and high computational power requirements.</p>	<p>Focused on integrating IoT, AI, and ML in precision agriculture.</p>

Human-Centered AI in Smart Farming: Toward Agriculture 5.0	Andreas Holzinger, Iztok Fister Jr., Iztok Fister Sr., Hans-Peter Kaul, And Senthold Asseng	Neural Networks (ANNs), CNNs, Deep Learning	Various farming-related data such as crop health monitoring.	Deep learning (DL) models used in image recognition and object detection have achieved high accuracy in detecting plant diseases.	Automation of tedious tasks, personalized recommendations based on real-time data, reducing labor costs.	Requires significant training data, potential over-reliance on automation.	Transition towards integrating AI for optimizing human-machine interaction in farming.
Machine Learning in Agriculture: A Review	Konstantinos G. Liakos, Patrizia Busato, Dimitrios Moshou, Simon Pearson and Dionysis Bochtis	Regression models, K-nearest neighbor (KNN), Random Forest, Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Deep Neural Networks	Sensor data for crop yield, soil nitrogen, water management, and livestock production.	Accuracy varies depending on the application. For example, Wheat yield prediction using ML achieved high prediction accuracy	High potential for predictive modeling, improved crop and livestock monitoring.	Model complexity, high data processing requirements.	Comprehensive analysis of ML applications across crop management, soil, and water.
A Systematic Literature Review of Machine Learning Techniques Deployed in Agriculture: A Case Study of Banana Crop	Priyanka Sahu, Amit Prakash Singh, Anuradha Chug, And Dinesh Singh	SVM, CNNs, Random Forest, and YOLOv4 are commonly used. CNNs and SVM show high accuracy for disease detection and ripeness.	Common datasets include PlantVillage, Godliver and Scotnelson, and proprietary field-collected datasets.	SVM achieved 80%-99.61% accuracy in disease detection, and 96%-99% in predicting ripeness and shelf-life.	High accuracy, real-time detection, and potential for automation.	Limited datasets, environmental challenges in real-world application, and computational complexity for CNNs.	ML techniques show strong potential in banana crop analysis but require better datasets and real-world testing.

	2022						
Application of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Agriculture	Sudeep Marwaha 2023	Deep Learning Models	used an open-source dataset named Plant Village (Hughes and Salathe 2016)	N/A	AI and ML can improve crop yields, reduce waste, and optimize resource use in agriculture	High costs, potential job losses, and concerns about data privacy and AI bias are some obstacles	This approach potentially helpful for the irrigation decision makers.
Applications of Machine Learning in Agriculture	Padmesh Tripathi January, 2023	genetic algorithm	Descriptive Statics	prevention of paddy soil degradation.	optimizes resource usage, reducing costs and environmental impact.	Requires high-quality data for accurate models, which can be challenging to obtain in rural areas.	It is extensively used to solve complicate problems in agriculture
Machine Learning In Agriculture : A Review	Azeem Ayaz Mirani May 2021	Machine learning algorithms (i-e SVM, DT, ANN etc.)	SVM, Random forest and decision trees)	High accuracy in real-time classification	Early identification of plant diseases using image analysis, improving crop health and preventing significant losses.	Requires high-quality, consistent data for accurate models, which can be challenging to obtain in rural areas.	This study Presented to highlight machine learning applications and its important in agriculture crop yield prediction.

Machine Learning in Agriculture	Gatkal N. R	ML Algorithms	a sizable dataset of photos of healthy and sick plants is required for precise image classifiers for disease identification.	Its ability to automate and improve the accuracy of complex tasks.	resource allocation (water, fertilizer) based on specific field conditions, leading to increased yields and reduced costs.	Requires high-quality, consistent data for accurate models, which can be challenging to obtain in rural areas.	Machine learning has the potential to revolutionize agriculture by increasing efficiency and productivity while reducing costs
“MACHINE LEARNING FOR PRECISE CROP MANAGEMENT IN AGRICULTURE: A REVIEW”	Parmar Rinkesh April2022	ANN, SVR, KNN, RF etc	ANNs are distinguished by their ability to develop relationships between dependent and independent variables and thus extract useful information from representative datasets	85%	Forecasting crop yields based on historical data and current conditions, aiding in planning and decision-making.	Developing complex machine learning models can be computationally intensive and require specialized expertise.	The current systematic review study focuses on ML in agriculture, which is a growing topic around the world.
A Comprehensive Review on	Various Authors, 2021	Various algorithms including SVM, ANN, and RF	Diverse datasets from agricultural environment	Improved monitoring and prediction accuracy	Enables real-time monitoring of environmental	Handling and analyzing large volumes of	Focuses on the integration of smart sensing

Smart Sensing Technology for Monitoring and Predicting Agricultural Environment			ts	Varies by algorithm and application	factors, leading to optimized resource management and improved crop yields.	sensor data can be computationally intensive and require robust data management infrastructure	technology with machine learning for enhanced agricultural monitoring
Machine Learning In Agriculture : A Review	Muhammad Suleman Memon et al., 2021	Various algorithms including SVM, ANN, and DT	Agricultural datasets from different sources	Enhanced agricultural productivity and efficiency Varies by algorithm and application	Leveraging robotics and AI, machine learning can automate tasks like planting, harvesting, and weeding, reducing labor costs and improving efficiency.	The use of autonomous systems in agriculture raises ethical questions related to job displacement, environmental impact, and potential biases in decision-making algorithms.	Reviews the application of machine learning in various agricultural domains.
Weed Density and Distribution Estimation for Precision Agriculture Using SemiSupervised Learning	Shantam ShorewalaA rmaan Ashfaque, R. Sidharth, And Ujjwal Verma 2021	Semisupervised learning with classification model.	Mixed datasets depending on application	Focus on minimizing misclassification; specific values not detailed.	Enables targeted application of herbicides, reducing chemical use and environmental impact.	Weed density and distribution can vary significantly across fields and seasons, requiring robust models	Effective for site-specific weed management, reduces manual annotation effort
A Machine Learning Approach of Data Mining in Agriculture 4.0	Amit Thakur 2020	ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average)	Various algorithms including Decision Trees, Random Forest, and SVM	Agricultural data from various sources Not specified	Machine learning can analyze historical data to predict market trends, optimize inventory management, and improve	Combining data from various sources (e.g., weather, soil, crop, and market data) can be challenging due to inconsistencies	<u>Focuses on the application of machine learning in agriculture to improve productivity and efficiency</u>

					supply chain efficiency.	es in data formats and quality.	
Towards Sustainable Agriculture: Harnessing AI for Global Food Security	Dhananjay K. Pandey, Richa Mishra 2024	Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)	Various AI techniques	Global agricultural data	analyze satellite imagery to detect crop stress, pests, and diseases early, allowing for timely interventions to mitigate losses	Satellite imagery can be affected by cloud cover, limiting the frequency and quality of data collection.	Discusses the role of AI in ensuring global food security and addressing hunger and malnutrition
Educational Data Mining: Prediction of Students' Academic Performance Using Machine Learning Algorithms	Mustafa Yağcı 2022	Regression Analysis	Student Performance Dataset	Academic achievement grades of 1854 students 70-75%	By identifying individual student needs and strengths, machine learning can enable personalized learning paths and interventions to improve academic outcomes.	Ensuring the quality and completeness of student data is crucial for accurate predictions. Missing or inaccurate data can lead to biased models	<u>Predicts final exam grades based on midterm grades</u>
A Comprehensive Review on Automation in Agriculture Using Artificial Intelligence	Kirtan Jha, Aalap Doshi, Poojan Patel, Manan Shah 2019	Reinforcement Learning	Various AI techniques	Three different datasets 87%, 89%, and 80%	AI-powered automation can enable autonomous tractors, drones, and robots to perform tasks like planting, harvesting, and weed control, reducing labor costs and	Ensuring the safety and reliability of autonomous agricultural machinery is crucial, especially when operating in complex environments	<u>Effective in predicting student performance</u>

					improving efficiency	with potential hazards	
A Review of Evaluation Metrics in Machine Learning Algorithms	Gireen Naidu, Tranos Zuva, Elias Mmbongeni Sibanda 2023	Various algorithms	Any dataset relevant to the machine learning task	Not specified	Evaluation metrics provide valuable insights for selecting the best model and tuning its hyperparameters to optimize performance.	Choosing the appropriate evaluation metric can be challenging, as different metrics may emphasize different aspects of model performance	<u>Discusses the importance of standardized evaluation metrics in machine learning</u>
A Review of advanced Evaluation Metrics in Machine Learning Algorithms	Tranos Zuva, Elias Mmbongeni Sibanda 2023	including Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score, ROC/AUC, Kappa statistics	dataset relevant to the machine learning task	Not specified	Some advanced metrics can provide insights into the inner workings of machine learning models, helping to understand why a model makes certain predictions.	Advanced metrics can be computationally expensive to calculate, especially for large datasets or complex models.	<u>Highlights the need for standardized evaluation metrics in machine learning</u>
Review of Agricultural IoT Technology	Jinyuan Xu, Baoxing Gu, Guangzhao Tian 2022	IoT integrated with AI	Sensor Data	Various IoT datasets in agriculture	IoT-enabled sensors and data analytics can optimize resource allocation (e.g., water, fertilizer) based on real-time field conditions, leading to increased yields and reduced costs.	Handling and analyzing large volumes of sensor data can be computationally intensive and require robust data management infrastructure.	<u>Discusses the integration of IoT and AI to improve agricultural output and product quality</u>

Implementation of Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture for Optimisation of Irrigation and Application of Pesticides and Herbicides	Tanha Talaviya, Dhara Shah, Nivedita Patel, Hiteshri Yagnik, Manan Shah 2022	Reinforcement Learning	Sensor Data	Agricultural data for irrigation and pesticide application	AI-powered optimization can enable targeted application of water, pesticides, and herbicides, reducing waste and environmental impact.	Developing and training reinforcement learning models for agricultural applications can be computationally intensive and require significant expertise.	<u>Reviews the use of AI for automating agricultural processes to meet the demands of a growing population¹.</u>
AI and Machine Learning for Soil Analysis: An Assessment of Sustainable Agricultural Practices	Muhammad Awais, Syed Muhammad Zaigham Abbas Naqvi, Hao Zhang, 2023	Regression Analysis	Soil Sensor Data	Soil texture and soil-water content data	AI-powered soil analysis can enable targeted application of fertilizers, reducing nutrient runoff and improving crop yields	Ensuring the accuracy and calibration of soil sensors is crucial for obtaining reliable data.	<u>Evaluates the use of AI and ML for robust and accurate soil analysis to support sustainable agricultural practices².</u>
Automation and Digitization of Agriculture Using Artificial Intelligence and Internet of Things	A. Subeesh, C.R. Mehta 2021	Reinforcement Learning	Various agricultural datasets	60 to 80 percent accurate	AI-powered automation can enable autonomous tractors, drones, and robots to perform tasks like planting, harvesting, and weed control, reducing labor costs and improving efficiency.	to make sure that robots and machines used in farming are safe and work well, especially when they're in places that are difficult or dangerous	<u>Explores the role of AI and IoT in addressing challenges like population growth and climate change in agriculture¹.</u>

Proposed Systems

- I. **Crop Yield Prediction System:** This is a system that predicts agricultural yield using regression techniques and deep learning models. In this regard, a hybrid approach is taken in combining several algorithms aimed at giving improved outcomes to the prediction task. Here, it utilizes Decision Tree and XGBoost for regression to predict on the grounds of the sparse data handling capabilities of XGBoost. It predicts yield based upon historical data like rainfall, crop type, area, production, and meteorological conditions. Applying k-fold cross-

validation, this system ensures that the model is generalizing well across the different datasets and hence improves its robustness against various environmental conditions.

- II. **Precision Weed Control:** The other significant system proposed in the context of precision farming deals with the precision aspect of weed control which is supported by image classification algorithms in addition to the computer vision techniques. The proposed system contains data-driven models processing big datasets from drones and ground-based sensors. Among other things, it classifies the kind of weeds; therefore, herbicides can be applied in a more targeted manner, thus minimizing the environmental damage as well as operations costs. Real-time image processing and decision-making capabilities become an innovation point here to enable prompt intervention in the fields.

- III. **Crop Quality Monitoring:** It is proposed to design a crop quality monitoring system to assess the plant's health and quality at various stages of growth. System of ML techniques: Decision Trees and Regression Algorithms applied on real-time sensor data as well as satellite imagery to observe growth of crops, soil moisture, and progress of disease. This designed system will integrate environmental data into its operation by consolidating data on weather patterns and soil conditions with output history in agriculture. This hybrid system allows for dynamic changes in crop management to the benefit of the farmers by getting real-time advice.

- IV. **Multivariate Crop Yield System:** This is another designed system that maximizes yield predicting power, entailing a Multivariate Linear Regression model whereby multiple relations between several factors like rain falls, soil health, and type of crop are tested. The system distinguishes how different elements will affect the production since different regions represent different climatic conditions. The integration of crop data with the Parallel Layer Regression (PLR) model helps in giving more accurate predictions for different geographical regions and improves the skills associated with decision making in crop selection and resource use by farmers through.

- V. **Crop Productivity using Deep Belief Network:** For estimating crop productivity across different crops like rice, maize, and wheat, the paper brings out a Deep Belief Network (DBN) system. This model uses a hierarchical structure, in which it pre-processes the given data to eliminate all forms of noise and outliers before applying DBN for prediction purposes on crop yield. The system factors in more than one layer of hidden variables in modeling input factors, like soil features, ambient conditions, and crop history. The model has been verified to have high specificity and sensitivity in predicting yield for large samples.

Conclusion

Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) integration in agriculture holds a very significant potential for transformation, as can be seen below from the research articles. All these DL technologies of the next generation are transforming the very important agricultural practices of crop yield prediction, disease detection, weed control, and resource management. With direct use of algorithms such as Decision Trees, XGBoost, and other predictive models, decision-making can be made directly by the farmer to optimally enhance productivity and minimize losses and improve sustainability.

Probably, one of the main benefits of the ML and DL systems in agriculture is the ability to process vast amounts of data relating to the weather, soil, and health of the crops to produce highly accurate precipitation forecasts. Such systems hold great promise for increasing the quality and volume of agricultural output. However, its computation needs along with the requirement of large, high-quality datasets pose a significant challenge to deployment in resource-constrained settings.

However, the potential is enormous for developing automated systems that can monitor and even analyse in real time, act instantly, and monitor agricultural fields. As these ML and DL technologies evolve and improve continuously, it would be interesting to see this group now progressively being adopted to address global food security challenges, especially in the wake of climate change and population growth. In the research papers, this is indicated through the developing progress that will require further development so that the existing limitations in the ability to achieve the goals laid out would be overcome, paving the way for precision farming in a future where conditions would be even more efficient and sustainable.

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